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The Cultural Narratives of AIDS, Gay Sexuality, and Family in Colm Tóibín's *The Blackwater Lightship*

Set in early 1990s rural Ireland, Colm Tóibín's *The Blackwater Lightship* (1999) concerns itself with three generations of a family and their need to overcome old conflicts. The novel tells the story of Declan, a young gay man in his twenties dying of AIDS. His illness and impending death become the catalyst for his reunification with his grandmother Dora, his mother Lily, and his sister Helen at their house in Cush, the locus of familial breakdown in the past. They are also joined by Declan's gay friends, Paul and Larry, who acted as his surrogate family during his earlier stages of AIDS.

As is the case in his two first novels, *The South* and *The Heather Blazing*, Tóibín explores in *The Blackwater Lightship* some of his favourite topics: the fractured family, the dichotomy between past and present, as well as the tensions between revealing and concealing one's own intimate emotions. As critics have pointed out (McMullen, 2004; Persson, 2007; Murphy, 2009; Costello-Sullivan, 2012; Walshe, 2013), in this novel Tóibín also remakes received discourses on the family, homosexuality and AIDS, advocating a more tolerant society. Eibhear Walshe, for instance, commends Tóibín for his inclusion of a sympathetic AIDS narrative within the Irish literary panorama: "Tóibín does achieve a cultural centrality for the discourse of AIDS, almost single-handedly in Irish fiction" (2013: 91). Moreover, in *The Blackwater Lightship*, Tóibín challenges deep-seated homophobic prejudices by having Declan's friends expressing their personal accounts and family struggles. As I will argue here, their sincere attachment to their friend is also recognised, as well as their rightful place within Declan's family and, allegorically, within Irish society. In this respect, Robinson Murphy rightly notes how Tóibín here "re-imagines definitions of 'Irish' and 'family' and offers instead a model of inclusiveness" (2009: 495).

Significantly, with its inclusion of gay characters telling their life stories, Tóibín's progressive novel foreshadows the cultural climate surrounding the referendum of May

2015, when Ireland became the first country in the world to legalise same-sex marriage by popular vote. One particular characteristic of the campaign was the public dissemination of personal testimonies within communities and in the media. In *Ireland Says Yes*, Gráinne Healy, Brian Sheehan and Noel Whelan explain how:

The referendum campaign required hundreds of gay and lesbian people, their parents, and their adult children to become champions for family diversity. Hundreds wrote letters to newspapers, posted on social media or started conversations about why marriage equality mattered and why all children and parents should be treated equally. (2016: 111)

As Healy, Sheehan and Whelan relate, LGTB campaigners shared their hopes and experiences with the wider society, and this, in turn, helped them gain the sympathy of many heterosexuals, whose support became indispensable for the success of the “yes vote”. In the light of all this, I see Tóibín’s 1999 novel as enacting the type of understanding, acceptance and inclusion that the 2015 referendum fostered on a national level for homosexuals. Curiously, just as Tóibín expands the language of the family in *The Blackwater Lightship*, the same occurred in Ireland thanks to the legalisation of same-sex marriage. Likewise, in his “post-referendum” article, O’Toole frames Ireland’s validation of homosexual love within an inclusive language of family and community: “There is no ‘them’ anymore. LGTB people are us –our sons and daughters, mothers and fathers, brothers and sisters, neighbours and friends” (“Tolerance”, 2015).

Given the fact that *The Blackwater Lightship* can be considered one of the cultural landmarks of Irish gay sexuality in recent history¹, in this chapter I will focus on Tóibín’s representation of AIDS and homosexuality in the context of 1990s Ireland. Coincidentally, I will argue how, in visibilising gay subjectivities, Tóibín brings to light the limitations of the dominant heteronormative family model.

Prior to considering the social attitudes towards AIDS and homosexuality in 1990s Ireland, I would like to reflect briefly on the cultural implications of homophobia and heterosexism. In today’s world, homosexuality still remains a complicated issue which provokes confronted opinions in societies where heterosexuality is the norm. Heterosexism, therefore, hampers the social normalisation of homosexuals in their

¹ In his article advocating a yes vote in the same-sex marriage referendum, Eibhear Walshe names Tóibín’s *The Blackwater Lightship* as one of the “10 milestones in Irish gay rights” (“10 Milestones in Irish Gay Rights, 2015).

struggle for equal civil rights. According to Gregory Herek, heterosexism entails “the cultural ideology that perpetuates sexual stigma by denying and denigrating any non-heterosexual form of behavior, identity, relationship, or community” (2004: 16). In his general discussion of social attitudes towards homosexuals, Herek also quotes an interview with George Weinberg, who published in 1972 *Society and the Healthy Homosexual*, one of the first books to theorise about the causes and nature of “homophobia”. In this interview, Weinberg describes homophobia as “a fear of homosexuals which seemed to be associated with a fear of contagion, a fear of reducing the things one fought for –home and family. It was a religious fear and it had led to great brutality” (7). Interestingly, Weinberg invokes here the institution of the family, which has been used as a moral principle of order and justice that must be protected from the polluting influence and “immoral” behaviour of homosexuals.

As I have remarked in the first chapter, the cultural significance of the so-called “Catholic” family has been paramount in Ireland, since “visible adherence to Catholic moral doctrine on family and sexuality was adopted as a marker of difference” (Fahey, 2014: 73). Considering the Church’s cultural and political authority in Irish society until relatively recently, the Catholic conceptualisation of the family as necessarily heterosexual could only hinder any efforts to normalise homosexuality and render it visible. Thus, it should be noted that, when it comes to sexual morality, the Catholic Church has often taken pains to validate love and sex only within the confines of heterosexual marriage, to the obvious marginalisation of homosexuals². In fact, in Ireland, homophobia has partly derived from the great political and moral authority that the Church exercised for most of the twentieth century³. In *Lesbian and Gay Visions of Ireland*, Ger Moane denounces that “the Catholic Church remains the primary and most vocal source of condemnatory views of homosexuality, and has provided the main

² Sufficiently clear in this respect, the 2003 Pastoral Letter of the Irish bishops, entitled “Human Sexuality”, contends that “the witness of the Scriptures is consonant with a view that rejects homosexual practice of any kind, and that marriage between a man and a woman in life-long union remains the only appropriate place for sexual relations. This must remain the standard for Christian behaviour” (125).

³ Even though I pay special attention here to the Church because of its traditional central position in Ireland, it should be remarked that social hostility towards gays and lesbians does not happen exclusively within the domain of religion. In many countries, human rights do not apply to homosexuals, who too often become the victims of social exclusion, hate crimes and dehumanising antigay rhetoric. Discrimination against homosexuals also reaches the discourse of science. The World Health Organisation, for example, did not remove homosexuality from their list of mental disorders until the early 1990s. Prior to that date, Jennifer Terry relates how in The United States, as in many other countries, the medical control of homosexuals used to be characterised by “pyschiatrists’ inhumane use of psychopharmaceuticals, lobotomy, psychoanalysis and aversion therapy” (1999: 368).

justification for discrimination against, and hatred of, homosexual men and lesbians” (1995: 88).

One of the justifications for this ostracism is the stereotypical association of homosexuality with “depraved” and compulsive sex. This view is discussed by Tom Inglis in his *Lessons in Irish Sexuality* when he analyses the predominant ideas on homosexuality in late twentieth-century Ireland: “The message is that gays and lesbians cannot relate to others in any way other than through their genitals [...] Any form of communication or affection is a means of fulfilling an uncontrollable sex drive” (1998: 160). Obviously, by ignoring or negating the possibility of love and stable relationships between homosexuals, homophobes regard homosexuality as a pathological condition. In this process, gays and lesbians become, to some extent, dehumanised by a moral discourse that denigrates them.

Due to this history of discrimination, it is hardly surprising that homophobia was persistent in 1990s Irish society despite the decriminalisation of male homosexuality in 1993 and the increasing modernisation of the country. It should be noted that, even if this legal reformation was a fundamental step in the acceptability of homosexuals, decriminalisation could not ensure social equality: “Although gay men were now allowed their private sexuality, public space was still treacherous for both gays and lesbians” (Conrad, 53). Being publicly gay or lesbian often becomes an issue for many homosexuals, who feel that they cannot be open about their sexuality. Writer Emma Donoghue also offers the following observation: “I know a lot of people who are very out and proud when they’re in Dublin, but back home down the country not a word to the family, and it might be the same about jobs, so there’s a lot of living in two worlds” (cited in Jeffers, 2002: 93). Interestingly, for Donoghue, the intimate space of the family becomes a contentious area for homosexuals, who are, in many cases, unable to express their own identities freely for fear of rejection.

As has been outlined, social attitudes towards homosexuality in 1990s Ireland were characterised by widespread prejudice and narrow-mindedness. Michéal Mac Gréil’s 1997 survey reveals an alarming level of familial homophobia, as it was discovered that “only 12.5 percent of Irish people would welcome a gay person in their family” (343). According to Mac Gréil, homosexuals have been subject to strong antipathy and can certainly count as a marginalised social group: “The level of homophobia in Irish population is still very high and quite disturbing” (451). In *Occasions*

of *Sin*, Ferriter also pays attention to the insidious homophobia in the late 1990s and early 2000s Ireland, explaining that “research conducted in twenty-four countries between 1999 and 2002 suggested Ireland was one of the most homophobic countries in the western world” (2012: 509).

All these issues –the silencing of homosexuality, the preconceived notions regarding gay sexuality and homophobia in 1990s Ireland– will be reconsidered in my analysis of Tóibín’s novel. I contend that the author challenges heterosexist assumptions concerning homosexuality precisely through a “gay narrative” whose plot nevertheless develops within the boundaries of a “traditional” family. By so doing, Tóibín does not place homosexuality in opposition to the nuclear family; he rather points to the failure of heteronormative families and societies to accommodate gay sensibilities.

In *The Blackwater Lightship*, Tóibín also deals with the devastating reality of AIDS. As a sexually transmissible disease that destroyed the lives of thousands of homosexual men, AIDS and gay sexuality became closely interconnected in Western societies. Initially believed to be a “gay cancer” in the early 1980s (Epstein, 1996: 53), AIDS was soon associated with sexual “immorality” and the violation of social mores:

Reinforced by the mainstream media and filtering out into diverse arenas, the idea of linkage between homosexuality, promiscuity, and illness informed an emergent sensibility about the syndrome –a vision, sometimes an articulated perception, of the epidemic as somehow the product of ‘the homosexual lifestyle’. (Epstein, 52)

As Steven Epstein indicates, the virus was turned into a battleground of social debates on the perceived “evils” of sexual permissiveness and the need to contain the threat posed by a “homosexual lifestyle”. The public presentation of the epidemic generally placed all the blame on those infected with the virus, so the victims of AIDS too often had to confront the additional burden of shame and social antipathy⁴.

⁴ Writing in 1989 in an American context, Douglas Crimp called for social activism in the face of a humanitarian crisis that was being inadequately dealt with by the wider society: “Most people dying of AIDS are very young, and those of us coping with these deaths, ourselves also young, have confronted great loss entirely unprepared. The numbers of deaths are unthinkable: lovers, friends, acquaintances, and community members have fallen ill and died [...] Apart from the deaths, we contend with the gruesome illness itself, acting as caretakers, often for very extended periods, making innumerable hospital visits, providing emotional support [...] Through the turmoil imposed by illness and death, the rest of society offers little support or even acknowledgment. On the contrary, we are blamed, belittled, excluded, derided” (15).

Because of this social antipathy, the victims received little support from the wider society during the first years of the AIDS emergencies. Working from a position of marginality, lesbian and gay communities became essential “in providing social networks for support and campaigning, in developing a grammar for safer sex, in promoting a language of resistance and survival” (Weeks, 1995: 98). Even though in most Western societies gays and lesbians were judged as being solely interested in sex, homo-social bonding became indispensable in the provision of love and care to the victims.

As has also been the case in other countries, many Irish people have shared animosity and rejection towards AIDS victims, showing little sympathy for their predicament and suffering. Commenting upon the results of his 1997 survey, Mac Gréil points out that “the attitudes of respondents towards ‘People with AIDS’ is extremely negative [...] Such severity is difficult to comprehend in relation to people who are in need of community support” (451). One of the reasons for this attitude towards AIDS was its identification with homosexuality and promiscuity in a society which has traditionally proscribed sex and punished sexual transgressions: “The association of ‘Gay People’ with AIDS is probably another negative factor” (Mac Gréil, 451).

In his study on cultural representations of AIDS, Cormac O’Brien makes an important distinction in terms of social attitudes in contemporary Ireland:

Ireland bifurcates into two paradoxical socio-cultural discourses: that of HIV as a medical event, and that of AIDS as a cultural narrative. Medical discourse and practices are progressive and democratic [...] On the other hand, the national epistemology underwriting AIDS as an Irish cultural narrative is steeped in contagion paranoia, and tainted by deeply embedded institutional stigma towards HIV-positive citizens. (2013: 75)

As we shall see in *The Blackwater Lightship*, Tóibín prefers to put the focus on an Irish progressive discourse on AIDS, projecting an image of a society that has learnt to treat HIV-positives with respect and dignity. Nevertheless, since “the contagion paranoia” is deeply embedded in Irish society (O’Brien, 75), Tóibín himself in the early 1990s wrote an article decrying the ways in which the Irish mass media dealt with the illness, with TV panelists exaggerating the danger and giving the impression that they did not want even to be touched by people with the AIDS virus. Tóibín critiques this limited understanding of the epidemic whilst pointing out that “it is essential for everyone to understand that

those who are HIV positives should be surrounded with a general air of normality” (“Time to be positive about AIDS”, 1991).

Notably, *The Blackwater Lightship* is not a first for Tóibín’s fictional engagement with gay sexuality and AIDS in a repressive society. He had done so previously in *The Story of the Night* ([1996] 2010), a novel set in 1980s Argentina. Here, Tóibín depicts gay romance in a time of darkness and secrecy, with the protagonist, Richard, finding love and companionship in his boyfriend, Pablo. In one of the most emotive scenes of the book, Richard takes Pablo to the cemetery and introduces him to his deceased parents:

I asked him to come with me to my parents’ grave [...] I spoke to them in my mind as we stood over their grave. I told them about Pablo and how much in love with him I was and how happy I felt [...] I feel loved again and secure, I said. Do you remember how I always wanted a brother, I asked them. Well, I have one now and I love him. (198)

Their relationship, however, becomes threatened by the fatal discovery of AIDS and the trauma attached to it. As is revealed, each of them had contracted the virus long before they had met, but they now start to suffer the consequences of the illness. They stick together and, despite all the pain and infirmities that they are going through, Richard claims that “[he] was more in love with Pablo than [he] had been in all the time [they] were together” (303).

Crucially, novels like *The Story of the Night* have served to expand the public language of homosexual love and romance, achieving new levels of insight and understanding. Writing for *The Irish Times* in the context of the referendum campaign for the legalisation of same-sex marriage, Tóibín recalls a personal anecdote connected with the reception in Ireland of his first gay novel:

In 1996, after I had published my novel *The Story of the Night*, which is in part an account of the love between two men, I received a private letter from one of the most powerful men in Ireland, someone who had served in government [...] He simply said that it had never occurred to him that two men could fall in love in the way straight people do. He had thought being gay was merely about sex. (“Referendum”, 2015)

The letter that Tóibín received, written by a prominent Irish politician, illustrates the heterosexist culture of 1990s Ireland, when gay love was not socially recognised and there was a widespread ignorance about the realities surrounding homosexuality.

Drawing on the social context of 1990s Ireland, I will analyse in this chapter the ways in which Tóibín addresses the issues of AIDS and gay sexuality in *The Blackwater Lightship*. The novel opens with Helen –Declan’s sister– and her domestic life in Dublin with her husband, Hugh, and their two sons, Cathal and Manus. Just after her husband departs with their two children for holidays, one of her brother’s friends, Paul, visits Helen to inform her about Declan’s HIV condition and his struggle with the last stages of AIDS. Appalled by the news, Helen cannot avoid feeling an “intense hostility” toward this stranger (32), but she then reasons that her brother’s friends may well consider her “an outsider, a remote figure who had to be brought into the picture” (34). Helen had kept little contact with her brother; she did not even know whether he was living alone or had a boyfriend. She also tells us that “it was years since she had met any of Declan’s friends” (30). Significantly, early in the novel, by having Helen admitting to herself that her brother “had replaced his family with his friends” (34), Tóibín makes a powerful statement on the incomprehension that many gays have experienced, their need to seek support outside their families, the stigma of their sexuality and the shameful condition of AIDS victims in the Irish society. At the same time, the writer markedly contrasts the biological family’s initial disunity with the closeness and comfort supplied by Declan’s friends, who had accompanied him to hospital on many occasions and know how to take care of him.

In its provision of love and support, gay friendship acquires here a meaning that has been conventionally attached to the nuclear, heterosexual family. But, most vitally, Tóibín’s presentation of an “alternative family” –based on the creation of relationships sustained by firm principles of solidarity– undermines the heterosexist beliefs which presuppose that a community’s stability depends on the cultural and social reproduction of heterosexuality. As Peter M. Nardi observes,

The traditional, nuclear family has been the dominant model for political relations and has structured much of the legal and social norms of our culture [...] For many gay people, the ‘friends as family’ model is a political statement, going beyond the practicality of developing a surrogate family in times of needed social support. (1992: 117)

Whereas Michael G. Cronin appreciates little subversive potential in *The Blackwater Lightship*, as he explains that Tóibín “contains sexual identity within the territory of the familial and the domestic” and imagines Ireland’s gay subculture “as based on affective bonds rather than political solidarity” (2004: 258, 261), I contend that Tóibín’s foregrounding of gay affective bonds within the territory of the family becomes a gesture of political significance. Through his “friends as family” model, the writer helps transform public perceptions on gay sexuality and the family. This becomes especially relevant in a country like Ireland, where, until relatively recently, “a systematic control and repression of homosexuality through the law, medicine and religious doctrine had been the only visible cultural identity for gay men” (Walshe, 2006: 127).

Apart from Tóibín’s meaningful configuration of a gay family for Declan, another relevant characteristic of *The Blackwater Lightship* is the way in which his biological family welcomes him, showing no moral reproach. Significantly, Tóibín’s depiction of the nuclear family produces a model empathy that, unfortunately, was denied to too many HIV-positives at that time, the 1990s, when the experience of the AIDS epidemic often “underscored the family’s inability –or rather, in many cases, its unwillingness– to deal with its own responsibilities where gay men are concerned” (Woods, 1998: 355). In the story, when Helen visits Declan in hospital, the brother reveals his desire for a family reunion at their house in Cush. Therefore, he asks his sister to break the news of his status to their mother, Lily, and grandmother, Dora. On being informed, Lily and Dora react with respect and responsibility towards Declan’s predicament. Dora, the grandmother, is not judgmental and compares AIDS to cancer in a conversation with Helen: “Nothing can be done. It was the same years ago with your father’s cancer. There was nothing the doctors could do. And poor Declan’s only starting his life” (47). Dora’s attitude can certainly be deemed a progressive one, as the cultural narratives of both diseases differed greatly: AIDS was often tinged with guilt and shame, whereas cancer was not. Lily’s first reaction upon seeing Declan also manifests her commitment to love her son through sickness: “We’re only here to make everything nice for you” (101).

Even if she displays an attitude of full cooperation and concern for her son’s welfare, Lily cannot bring herself to discuss the matter of Declan’s sexuality and refuses to talk to him about it. It is at hospital where the mother privately speaks with the doctor and asks her whether her son is homosexual. Perhaps due to its shameful associations, Lily cannot even utter the word “gay”, so she instead asks Helen “how long [she] [had]

known that [Declan] had friends like Paul” (110). The question, as she formulates it, denotes her reticence to tackle matters of sexuality directly. Interestingly, through the character of Lily, Tóibín invokes the sexually repressive culture of 1930/1940s Ireland, the generation to which Declan’s mother belongs. Inglis points out that:

The denial of sexuality in previous generations has had the effect of inculcating in older people an incompetence in talking [...] about the sexual aspects of their lives [...] The dominance of the Church in Irish society, particularly in education, had the consequence of preventing open, honest discussion about sexuality. (1998: 166)

Likewise, Dora shares her daughter’s “incompetence” in talking about sexuality and avoids using the word “gay”. In a conversation with Declan’s friends, the grandmother articulates commonly held prejudices and makes a clear distinction between straight and gay people, as well as their respective lifestyles: “Declan never told us anything about himself. We always thought that he had a great life in Dublin. No one knew he was sick and no one knew he was one of you” (142).

Neither Dora nor Lily knew about Declan’s sexuality or had asked him about it. The fact that Declan was openly gay in Dublin but “in the closet” back home also mirrors the experiences of many homosexuals who fear familial homophobia and therefore remain silent about their sexuality. Another form of silence is employed during their stay in Cush, when the family tacitly agrees that they should hide Declan’s sexuality and health condition from the prying eyes of their neighbours:

‘And isn’t Declan looking very thin?’ Madge said. ‘He’ll never get a wife if he doesn’t fatten up a bit.’

‘Oh I’d say there are girls only waiting for him to make up his mind,’
Essie said and smiled sourly.

Neither Lily nor Helen spoke. (246)

No matter how modern this family may become, old habits and prejudices still linger. Thus, whilst portraying images of a more open-minded Ireland, Tóibín simultaneously depicts the shame and concealment concerning homosexuality and other realities such as AIDS, a disease culturally connected with “depravity” and gay promiscuity. As he often does in his gay fictions, Tóibín traces the gradual and sometimes difficult process of the normalisation of homosexuality.

As Helen, Dora and Lily adapt themselves to their new situation, Paul and Larry drive to the house in Cush to join the family and help Declan. Despite initial tensions and difficulties, Declan's biological and alternative families eventually come together as one functional unit. As readers soon learn, the two friends' stay in the house proves to be essential for the well-being of Declan. They not only bring the drugs that Declan may need but they also know how to deal with the situation when their friend becomes sick. Their generosity becomes a lesson for the rest of the family: "When Larry and Paul change Declan's soiled sheets with regard for nothing other than their friend's dignity, Helen and her mother learn something more about the language and practice of love" (Thurston, 2003: 652).

Of the three women, Lily remains the least tolerant of Declan's friends, even if she gradually learns to treat Paul respectfully and becomes "grateful that he knew what to do" when Declan's health deteriorates even further (254). In an episode in which Paul rebukes her for "getting in the way" whilst the two friends were giving Declan basic assistance (223), Lily openly resents Paul's "usurpation" of her mothering role and confronts him aggressively. This provokes a quarrel between the two, with Paul telling the mother that:

'Listen, Mrs Breen,' Paul said, 'I'm here as long as Declan is here and you can take that as written in stone [...] He is also concerned about you and loves you and wants your approval. He is also very sick. So stop feeling sorry for yourself, Mrs Breen.' (223)

Lily recoils from arguing and exits the room in tears, regretfully aware that she had failed for many years to behave as a close and nurturing parent. This episode also acquires further significance because Tóibín has Paul voicing Declan's desire to reconnect with his own mother despite the distance that he had maintained from her. Thus, these two friends help release unspoken feelings within the family at moments when gestures of unity and emotional honesty are strongly needed. Along the narrative, Paul and Larry not only become instrumental in helping Dora, Lily, Helen and Declan, but they also catalyse self-reflection and healing within the family.

As the members of this hitherto distant family spend days together, they also come to discover some of the experiences of homosexuals in Ireland, aspects of life that had been silenced by mainstream society. With Helen and Dora as listeners, Larry is the first one to recount his own story, starting with the trouble that he faced trying to hide his

sexuality at home while being an activist for the rights of gay people before decriminalisation in Dublin. Through Larry's personal account, Tóibín subverts the ideal of the unconditional love stereotypically attached to biological kinship, since, unfortunately in 1990s Ireland, the level of familial homophobia was extremely high and many homosexuals suffered rejection and incomprehension on the part of their parents (MacGréil, 343). Larry's "coming out" to his family is, in fact, tainted with a profound lack of support and understanding. They accept him as long as his sexuality is not mentioned, which prevents him from developing a close and honest relationship at home. Hence, Larry's parents may count as being part of a heterosexist and self-regarding society that chooses to close its eyes to the realities of homosexuals. Though pained, he tackles his own case of familial despondency with wry humour, telling the others that his mother "would have been happier if [he] had been in the IRA [...] It'd be more normal" (146).

In the second part of Larry's story, Tóibín unsettles the hypocritical façade of heterosexist Ireland and shows same-sex desire as being more common than generally believed. Larry talks about his sexual life and his having had sex on different occasions with four brothers belonging to a traditional and deeply religious family: "two of [the brothers] are married, but that doesn't seem to stop them" (147). This story of married men having sex with other men clearly shocks Dora, whose perplexity and disconcert illustrate a long Irish tradition of silence and shame surrounding sexual transgressions and same-sex desire:

'I told you that you wouldn't want to hear it, Mrs Devereux,' Larry said.

'Oh guard your heart, that's my advice to you, guard your heart and be careful of yourself.' (148)

More reserved than Larry, Paul has his own story to tell, but he shares it only with Helen. Through this character, Tóibín reveals other spheres of homosexual experience, such as school bullying, mob behaviour and the difficult process of gay sexual awakening. In his teenage years, Paul met François –his current partner– thanks to an exchange scheme, when they shared the same room in boarding school. Because of all the teasing against Paul due to his perceived effeminacy, they both became the object of cruel gossip among the schoolmates. On seeing this, François's courageous response was to strengthen his friendship with Paul. They became very close when Paul went for a month to his house

in France: this was, for both them, a time of “pure happiness” (167). In spite of their growing intimacy and romantic attachment, Paul’s personal acceptance of his sexual orientation took time and much psychic strain –it was not until his early twenties that he “had done [something] about it” (167), when his friendship with François evolved into a love relationship.

As a progressive novel for its time, Tóibín’s *The Blackwater Lightship* significantly features a homosexual wedding sixteen years before same-sex marriage was made legal in Ireland by referendum. This wedding, however, does not take place in Ireland, but in Belgium, where Paul and François live together. There, they both practice an alternative form of Catholic faith which treats homosexuals as equals and not as deviant people in desperate need of moral correction. Having found an accepting priest in Brussels, Paul marries François. Paul proposed marriage to him when François was suffering from depression because of the tragic loss of his parents and his fear of being abandoned, which demonstrates Paul’s strong bond with his soul-mate. Even if their marriage is not officially recognised by the Church, Paul feels that they have received “a very special grace” (173). Opposing the homophobic beliefs that reduce homosexuality to a kind of “immoral” sexual behaviour, Tóibín portrays Paul and François as a couple embodying the ideals of love preached by the Catholic Church, ideals which are based on monogamy and everlasting commitment.

Significantly, then, in *The Blackwater Lightship*, the concept of marriage –which, at the time Tóibín wrote the novel, was culturally encoded as exclusively heterosexual– is reframed and its meaning enlarged, as it includes a homosexual couple⁵. Tóibín also shows how, even if they got married in Belgium, Paul “imports” this version of European modernity to his own country by bringing his husband to Ireland: “I brought [François] home and reintroduced him to all my family, including my brothers, as my partner and my lover” (170). Paul, thus, makes an effort to integrate François into his biological family, giving social validation to their marriage. Since the two spouses are themselves practising Catholics, their refusal to be placed “outside” the established parameters of romantic love and their own redefinition of family become exceptionally relevant. Both

⁵ This redefinition of terms and ideas conventionally associated with heterosexuality can eventually lead to a new language of tolerance and inclusiveness: “The appropriation of the language of the family by many non-heterosexuals can [...] be seen as a battle over meaning, one important way in which the sexually marginal are struggling to assert the validity of their own way of life” (Weeks, Heaphy and Donovan, 2001: 17).

Paul and François reconcile their religious faith with their being openly gay, perceiving no contradiction between these two aspects of their lives.

At home in Brussels, Paul and François not only live on their own as a loving couple, but they also receive the visits of Declan and enjoy his company: “He was like a small boy, and he’d talk and doze and play with our feet. François always joked about adopting him [...] Declan loved being fed and looked after and listened to and protected from his former lovers by us”⁶ (174-5). In his review of *The Blackwater Lightship*, Terry Eagleton draws attention to Paul and François’s care of Declan, referring to the novel as a text about mothering where “the most proficient at the task turn out to be a couple of homosexual men” (1999). Furthermore, it is my contention that Tóibín symbolically defends here the legitimacy of homosexual parenthood, to this day illegal in most countries and frequently judged as a modern perversity which violates the very foundations of family and society. Thus, Tóibín refuses to conform to traditional convention and arbitrary judgments and offers instead a homosexual couple which does fulfill the moral and spiritual values often attached specifically to heterosexual marriage and parenthood.

Taken together, the personal histories of both Larry and Paul reflect upon circumstances that are intimately correlated to their being gay in a society that punishes sexual “deviance”. Though Paul and Larry have been through hard times, they eventually achieve some sense of confidence and self-affirmation with regard to their sexuality. As Persson remarks, “Paul and Larry come to represent gay suffering and gay triumph [...] Their oral histories [...] could be read as a strategy to resist dominant and official versions of what constitutes sexual identity and family” (150).

Declan, however, remains the one whose future will be destroyed by the stark reality of AIDS. Some critics have interpreted Declan’s impending death as “a kind of blood sacrifice to re-cement familial bonds” (Eagleton, 1999) or a punishment for his “reckless behaviour in Brussels” (Jeffers, 114), whereas his body is seen as the “site of Catholic morality and repression” (Yebra, 2014: 99). Walshe further argues that “some of the novel’s strengths as an AIDS narrative come at the expense of the representation of the homoerotic and of a contemporary Irish gay subjectivity”, due to the fact that

⁶ This vignette of domestic life finds its parallel later in the novel, when Lily remembers that Declan as a child used to do the same with his parents: “He would crawl all over us, he’d pull his daddy’s ears, or he’d want to tickle his feet” (243).

Declan “has no gay subjectivity beyond his bodily frailty: no boyfriend, no lover, no named sexual partners, no erotic past” (2006: 129). Though it is true that Tóibín only offers some glimpses of Declan’s sexual past, I contend that Declan’s “de-sexualisation” does not necessarily translate itself into the erasure of his gay subjectivity. It is significant that, in his search of personal communion and acceptance, Declan comes to his family and reveals himself as a gay man dying with the virus. And, for him to do this, he counts on the unconditional support of his “other family”, his gay friends, whose presence in Cush he demands. Even if Tóibín has his character remaining silent on his sexual past, I read Declan’s attempt to reveal his other life as a homosexual man as an expression of gay subjectivity. It is my argument that, now that he has to confront his impending death, Declan’s failed relationships and past sexual experiences seem to have become irrelevant.

Neither do I see Declan’s infection as being portrayed as a punishment for his sexual behaviour, as some critics have argued (Jeffers, 2002; Yebra, 2014). My interpretation is that Tóibín –as he had previously done in *The Story of the Night*– simply maintains an honest engagement with the realities of the disease. AIDS actually spread rapidly among gay men because of unsafe sex and multi sex partnering, and these practices seem to be the story behind Declan’s contraction of the virus. Tóibín does not deny those conditions of infection, nor does he occlude his character’s frail bodily condition. Nonetheless, it is remarkable that Tóibín chose not to have Declan as a mere vessel of regret and trauma. In fact, the writer infuses Declan with a keen sense of stoicism and bravery. Helen notices that his face “was almost green; she had not seen him looking so sick and so strained before. But he was smiling now and laughing. She realized as she watched him that he was making an effort to keep going” (247). Declan’s characterisation as gentle and good-humored helps soften the angst derived from his terminal illness, granting him a “human dimension” that goes beyond his suffering as an AIDS victim⁷. But, most importantly, there is no sense of moral reproach or “punishment” towards Declan in the novel. As has been previously outlined, AIDS victims too often suffered incomprehension and cruel rejection. In Tóibín’s text, however, Declan is never deprived of his dignity.

⁷ Because of the devastating effects of AIDS and the stigma attached to it, the victims’ social identity was too often bound up with the fatal disease and its moral connotations. Protesting against how the illness was being publicly presented, Tóibín himself comments in an interview that all human lives are complex and cannot be reduced to a particular condition: “People presumed that if someone had AIDS, that that was his essential narrative. Every time I came across it and thought about it –I had very close friends who died from AIDS, this was a very grim time– it seemed real nonsense” (Wiesenfarth, 2009: 7).

I also argue that, contrary to homophobic beliefs that relegate gay sexuality and AIDS to abjection and repudiation, Tóibín reclaims and humanises the gay/AIDS-ridden body. This is illustrated in the last pages of the novel, when Declan has to return to St James' hospital in Dublin for new treatment due to severe stomach cramps. Before he is taken to hospital, Declan is racked with an unbearable pain that has him awake all night, crying out loud. As Lily nurses him, Declan verbalises his long-desired return to the mother:

As Lily wiped his face and forehead and held his hands, and talked to him softly, he began to call out under his breath and, when the next attack came, Helen for the first time understood what he was saying.

He was saying: 'Mammy, Mammy, help me, Mammy.' (258)

This union with his mother certainly becomes a heart-wrenching moment of both pain and relief, with the ailing son eventually breaking down the emotional barriers that had been erected over time. In my reading of this scene, I see Declan's sick body as becoming the site in which the universal human need for love, belonging and acceptability is enacted. As the novel closes, readers share Declan's plight and are drawn to empathy and compassion.

To conclude, in this analysis of Tóibín's *The Blackwater Lightship*, I have paid attention to how the author challenges the stereotypes and heterosexist assumptions that were dominant in 1990s Ireland. As mentioned in the introduction to this chapter, social attitudes to gay sexuality in 1990s Ireland included the idea that homosexuals could not love one another and that they were guided by an uncontrollable sex drive. Since the public language of love and romance rarely included homosexuals, gays and lesbians were often regarded as inimical to the moral values which have traditionally been seen as constitutive of the institution of the family. Representatives of the Church in Ireland, for instance, have frequently considered homosexuality as alien to family life and as a dangerous and evil instinct that must be tamped down. These homophobic beliefs have for long damaged the self-image and dignity of homosexuals, many of them sharing personal histories of repression, secrecy and self-loathing. Despite their need of community support, many AIDS victims have also been shunned by family and society, as they were made to carry an additional burden of shame and rejection. The disease became associated with gay sexuality and inscribed within a cultural discourse of sexual guilt and punishment.

In *The Blackwater Lightship*, Tóibín removes the sexual stigma of AIDS, producing a narrative that focuses on how Declan “can and should be loved” (Wiesenfarth, 2009: 7). As has been outlined, the writer also remakes received notions of the family and offers a more inclusive model that accommodates gay subjectivities. Even though Tóibín does foreground the strong sentimental pull of the mother-son relationship through the final union between Declan and Lily, he concurrently gives ample space and recognition to Declan’s gay friends, who had been his alternative family all along. The two friends also help Declan reunite with his nuclear family, fractured as it was by resentment and lack of communication. In this context, the friends’ love for Declan and their cooperation with his hitherto distant family become essential for the well-being of their friend. Ultimately, through his portrayal of gay experiences and affective bonds, Tóibín reframes heterosexist and homophobic notions of family and community, promoting an ethics of inclusion in the face of a long history of repudiation, silence and intolerance towards homosexuals.

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